

The TU/e logo is displayed in large, blue, three-dimensional letters on the roof of a modern building with a glass facade. The background shows a cityscape at dusk with various buildings and trees.

Policy

Research Data Management Framework Policy

DATE

January 19, 2026

VERSION

9.5

The TU/e logo is presented in a white, bold, sans-serif font against a blue background.

EINDHOVEN
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Document information

Document number	1-0040
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PRELUDE

PROCESS AND IMPLEMENTATION PLAN OF THE RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK POLICY

Process: This policy comes as an overarching framework on how to manage research data. This policy will be used as a central point to link to other (existing) policies. This policy will be revised, and if required, amended at least every three years to remain up to date with novel developments in research data management practice, regulatory standards, and legislation.

Implementation plan:

PhD candidates: For research projects that start after September 2025, all PhD candidates will need to submit an approved data management plan (DMP) at the 9 months evaluation and as part of their PhD defence package in HoraFinita.

Externally funded research: All research funded by NWO, ZonMw, and ERC require a mandatory DMP before and during the research project.

Research that requires ethical approval: All research that uses data from humans (primary and secondary data collection) requires an Ethical Approval which includes a DMP.

Communication Campaign: A communication campaign to announce the Framework Policy will be prepared, including a one-pager on the most relevant things researchers need to know about how to manage their research data.

Product Area Research (PAR) Roadshows: PAR is planning to have 2 roadshows per year where we (as support services) go to each department and introduce our services, as well as this policy and its implementation plan.

Research Infrastructure: PAR also developed the infrastructure needed for researchers to implement these framework policy requirements, the [Research Cockpit](#). The [Research Cockpit](#) will also be used to monitor the compliance of this policy and will provide insights on different metrics (e.g. software tools used, type of data that will be processed, estimated storage capacity needed, legal requirements, etc.). However, it also serves as a one-stop-shop for researchers, and it also allows the service departments to improve service and support during a research project.

The [Research Cockpit](#) currently covers the planning phase of any research project. It guides and provides templates to researchers for Data Management Plans, Ethical Applications, and Privacy Checks.

The Research Archival Package Solution project will support researchers with long-term preservation of data underlying their published articles, this is to comply with the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

Dedicated support: Via the [Research Cockpit](#), researchers will have access to the support they need. Depending on their department they will be automatically linked to the data steward and ResearchIT consultant of their department, as well as any other resources needed. The data stewards and the open science (OS) office already provide an OS and RDM (including lessons on how to write a DMP) PROOF course.

1. Introduction

This framework policy is motivated by the notion that research data management cultivates:

- Best practices to **ensure the long-term reproducibility of scientific findings**.
- **The quality of the research process**.
- Responsible management of research data, including the **safe storage and safe processing of personal data and protection of intellectual capital developed by scientists across TU/e**.
- Improved practices for **meeting the demands of funders and publishers with respect to research data management and sharing**.

The TU/e Research Data Framework Policy supports the development of professional practices and policies for research data management across each of the departments at TU/e. It provides clear roles and responsibilities for researchers and research support staff regarding the management of research data.

This document serves as an overarching framework policy on managing research data from research projects of the TU/e. It is accompanied by guidelines for the practical implementation of this policy ([Appendix 1](#)). **In addition, each department can define its research data management policies and procedures specific to its own staff which must be in line with the requirements outlined in this policy.**

Research data is defined as any information created, collected, stored, and processed for research purposes, to produce and validate research results. Research data does not include physical objects, but it does include information/description about them. Research documentation, includes analysis scripts, models, algorithms, interview questions as well as interview answers, codebooks, software code, etc.

A research project is defined as a scientific endeavour to answer a research question(s). Examples of a research project are; externally funded research projects, PhD thesis, MSc Thesis, EngD Thesis, etc.

2. Principles and existing policies/guidelines:

At the basis of this policy are the following existing policies/guidelines, if at any point this policy is not clear, the following policies/guidelines supersede this policy:

- [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#)
- [Uitvoeringswet Algemene verordening gegevensbescherming \(AVG\)](#)
- [The Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#)
- [The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#)
- [TU/e Code of Scientific Conduct](#)
- [TU/e Privacy policy](#)
- [TU/e Security policy](#)

3. Basic practices of RDM:

Below are the basic practices of research data management. These should be followed when working with research data. These practices have a description and guidelines for implementation in the [Appendix](#).

- A [Data Management Plan \(DMP\)](#) or Data Management Protocol is maintained for all research projects. This document should be updated when necessary.
- Processing of (personal and confidential) data from humans requires approval from an ethical review board ([ERB](#)) and must be in compliance with the [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#).
- All research data generated or processed at TU/e are stored in solutions provided within the university [storage solutions](#) (either centrally or within the department / research group). Exceptions

- apply when the research is done in collaboration with external parties and the data does not leave those parties.
- iv. All research personal and IP-protected data are obtained and used in a [lawful manner](#).
 - v. Final research data must be accompanied by [documentation](#) following the [FAIR \(Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable\) principles](#) and deposited in a data repository, where required.
 - vi. For research integrity purposes, a [data package](#) containing the research data and documentation needed to understand and use the data from peer-reviewed publications, is archived and stored for a retention period of 10 years for non-medical data and 20 years for medical data (exceptions can apply).

4. Roles and Responsibilities

Principal investigator (PI) and/or Project Owner tasks:

1. Ensure that the basic elements of this policy are implemented throughout the whole research data life cycle (RDLC).
2. At the beginning of the project, create a data management plan (DMP) or protocol. The DMP should be updated when changes in the project occur (e.g. purpose of the project, methods, analysis tools, new data being collected, storage solutions, etc.). This task can be delegated at the discretion of the PI or Project Owner.
3. Ensure that all members of the research project, including students, are aware of the project's DMP or protocol, and attend the available training on research data management and the FAIR data principles.
4. When human participants and/or personal data is being processed:
 - Primary data collection. Obtain approval from the Ethical Review Board (ERB) or Medical Ethical Review Committee (METC) before the start of the data collection.
 - Secondary data collection (data obtained from a third party). The Ethical Review Board (ERB) or Medical Ethical Review Committee (METC) approval should be in place.
5. Adhere to contractual obligations including funding requirements regarding ownership of, and rights relating to, research datasets resulting from projects funded by or in collaboration with external agencies or (commercial) companies.
6. Ensure that any agreements with external funding agencies, commercial companies, or other third parties allow compliance with this Research Data Management Framework Policy.
7. Budget for the costs of research data management into financial project planning where possible.
8. Create and manage the data during and after the research. This may include data destruction when policy, legal, or contractual agreements on retention of data or prevailing reasons require this.
9. Archive the data once the research is published and/or at the end of the project.

Supervisors of PhD and Postdoc tasks:

1. Support their PhDs and Postdocs in the preparation of a DMP for managing research outputs throughout their study or provide the DMP if already available.
2. Make sure the data management plan or protocol is being followed.
3. Supervise and verify that PhDs and Postdocs take their role and responsibilities as given below.
4. Ensure that PhDs and Postdocs attend relevant training on research data management.

PhD and Postdocs tasks:

1. Make sure to follow the data management plan or protocol created by the PI or Project Owner. If there isn't one then you will need to create and update a data management plan for the research project, discuss it with your supervisor(s), and work accordingly.
2. When human participants and/or personal data is being processed (when not under the responsibility of a PI or Project Owner):
 - Primary data collection. Obtain approval from the Ethical Review Board (ERB) or Medical Ethical Review Committee (METC) before the start of the data collection.
 - Secondary data collection (data obtained from a third party). The Ethical Review Board (ERB) or Medical Ethical Review Committee (METC) approval should be in place.
3. Create and archive the data at the end of the project (when not under the responsibility of a PI or Project Owner).
4. Ensure that all relevant research data, scripts, code, and any materials related to published papers and/or the PhD thesis is appropriately documented and stored on university supported storage facilities following the FAIR data principles
5. Attend the relevant training in research data management if necessary.

Supervisors of EngD, MSc, and BSc students' tasks:

1. Ensure that the basic elements of this policy are implemented throughout the whole research cycle.
2. Support EngD, MSc, and BSc students in preparation of a DMP when human participants and/or personal data is being processed in the project (when not under the responsibility of the PI or Project Owner).
3. When human participants and/or personal data is being processed (when not under the responsibility of a PI or Project Owner):
 - Primary data collection. Obtain approval from the Ethical Review Board (ERB) or Medical Ethical Review Committee (METC) before the start of the data collection.
 - Secondary data collection (data obtained from a third party). The Ethical Review Board (ERB) or Medical Ethical Review Committee (METC) approval should be in place.
4. Adhere to contractual obligations regarding ownership of, and rights relating to, research datasets resulting from projects funded by or in collaboration with external agencies or commercial companies.
5. Arrange agreements on Intellectual Property (IP), copyright, and data confidentiality with the student within student projects.
6. Ensure that MSc and BSc students attend relevant training on research data management.
7. Supervise and verify that MSc and BSc deposit their research data as described in their DMP.

Project Development Officers (PDO) tasks:

1. Create awareness amongst researchers on research data management obligations in the proposal development phase, including possible RDM costs that should be budgeted.
2. Inform the relevant Research Data Steward and Research IT consultant about any relevant data questions, issues, or problems arising during a project definition or planning phase when necessary, by timely providing all the necessary information about the project with them.
3. Make sure relevant legal / contractual / funder requirements on research data management are shared with relevant researchers and/or the relevant Research Data Steward.

Project Managers tasks:

1. Create awareness amongst researchers on research data management obligations in the execution phase.
2. Inform the relevant Research Data Steward and Research IT consultant about any relevant data questions, issues, or problems arising during a project when necessary.
3. Guide researchers in the elaboration and updating of the Data Management Plan.
4. Guide researchers on the publication and/or archival process once project closed.

Research Data Stewards tasks:

1. Create awareness and explain to researchers the added value of good research data management.
2. Actively support the development and implementation of the department's research data management policy
3. Create or use existing DMP templates and guidelines, as well as support and review DMPs.
4. Advise on all RDM-related topics (data storage and sharing, data organization, funder requirements, metadata and documentation, FAIR, and data preservation).
5. Organize university-wide training events and design training materials. When necessary, create department-tailored training sessions/workshops.
6. Act as the first line of support and first point of contact in privacy for researchers within departments.
More specifically:
 - Advise researchers on compliance with privacy laws and regulations and internal privacy policies.
 - Increase the required privacy knowledge and privacy awareness among researchers who work with personal data works.
 - Support researchers with:
 - The Ethical Review Board (ERB) and Medical Ethical Review Committee (METC) procedure.
 - Pre-DPIAs and DPIAs.
 - Privacy statements and consent forms, following the TU/e templates;
 - Data agreements, following the TU/e templates;

The department board (Data Domain Owner) tasks:

1. Encourage good research data management based on this and the department-specific policy.
2. In cooperation with central support and infrastructure, facilitate that, within the department, there is appropriate infrastructure and the right tools for researchers to put good research data management into practice.
3. Facilitate necessary training and advocate that provisions are provided by research data management support, make researchers aware of the Research Data Management Framework Policy and department's Research Data Management Policy and equip them with adequate skills to adhere to it.
4. Appoint someone to act as a person responsible for research data, if both the responsible supervisors and PIs are no longer able to authorise the destruction of or have no authority to destruct research data.

A centralized overview of who to contact and who is the person in each department can be found in the [bestuurs- en beheersreglement TU/e](#).

5. Document history

Date	Version	Details of change(s)	Author(s)	Reviewed by	Approved date	Status
09/11/2023	1.0	Creation of the Policy	DS Product Owner		09/12/2023	Send for feedback to Data Steward Team
09/12/2023	2.1	Feedback form data stewards were incorporated	DS Product Owner	DS team	18/12/2023	Send for feedback to Product Area Research (PAR)
23/01/2023	2.2	Feedback from PAR incorporated	DS Product Owner	Product Area Research (RDI lab, RIT)	23/01/2023	Send for feedback to Library and Information Services
22/02/2024	3.0	Feedback from LIS incorporated	DS Product Owner	LIS (Data Management, Privacy, Security, Open Science, Ethics, PDOs, PMs)	22/02/2024	Send for feedback to researchers
21/05/2024	4.0	Feedback from researchers incorporated	DS Product Owner	Researchers from all departments (ERB members, Research Committees at BE, IE&IS, C&CE)	21/05/2024	Send to Management Team of LIS
12/08/2024	5.0	Prelude and small typos incorporated	DS Product Owner	PAR Lead	12/08/2024	Send to EB for approval
11/09/2024	6.0	One pager and feedback from EB incorporated	DS Product Owner	PAR Lead	11/09/2024	Send to MDC for approval
18/10/2024	7.0	Feedback from MDC incorporated	DS Product Owner	PAR Lead	18/10/2024	Waiting EB, MDC, UCC approval
16/12/2024	8.0	Clarification storage solutions	DS Product Owner	PAR Lead	16/12/2024	Waiting EB, MDC, UCC approval
13/02/2025	9.0	New template and fixed broken links	DS Product Owner	PAR Lead	13/12/2025	LIS MT sent for approval
18/02/2025	9.1		DS Product Owner	PAR Lead	17/02/2025	Approved by the LIS MT
23/05/2025	9.2	Feedback from Deans (MCS, ME, BE)	DS Product Owner	PAR Lead	23/05/2025	Send to Deans for approval
11/07/2025	9.3	Feedback Dean of MCS	DS Product Owner	PAR Lead	03/09/2025	Waiting UCC approval
18/09/2025	9.4	UCC approved	DS Product Owner	PAR Lead	18/09/2025	Adopted by the EB
19/01/2026	9.5	Typos and links updated	DS Product Owner	PAR Lead	19/01/2026	Published

Research Data Management Framework Policy one-pager

What does this Research Data Management Framework Policy means to me?

Requirement	Description	Resources
Data Management Plans (DMPs)	<p>For PhD: A Data Management Plan is required for all research projects starting from September 2025. The DMP must be added to the HoraFinita system in the following 2 stages of the PhD: <i>Approved DMP</i> at the 9-month evaluation <i>Approved DMP</i> in the PhD defense package</p> <p>For other research staff: A Data Management Plan is required for all research projects starting from September 2025.</p> <p>For BSc, MSc, and EngD: A DMP is only required for research projects that include data from humans.</p>	Research Cockpit
Ethical Approval	Mandatory ethical review by the Ethical Review Board (ERB) for all research involving human participants and/or processing personal data.	Research Cockpit
Secure Data Storage	All research data generated or processed at TU/e must be stored in university-provided solutions (central or departmental/research group storage).	Solution Searcher
Data Agreements	Mandatory data agreements for (personal or IP-protected) data sharing with external parties.	Research Cockpit
FAIR Data	Final research data must follow the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles and deposited in a data repository, where required.	How to make data FAIR
Data Package	Research data and documentation from published peer-reviewed articles must be archived in a data package.	RAPS

Appendix

These guidelines are for those who do research, and thus we refer to researchers as “you” below, they provide practical steps to ensure research data management is properly conducted in line with this framework policy.

1. Data Management Plan or Protocol

A data management plan (DMP) is a document that describes all research data management aspects of a project that you need to think about before the start.

Benefits of writing a DMP:

- It makes it easier to understand and practice data management. Outputs of projects that follow data management practices are easier to understand and use, which leads to more citation, reuse of data, higher impact, and faster growth of the research field.
- It makes you work more efficiently. By thinking about all the steps of the research before the start, you can proactively plan for challenges in your research, avoid duplicate steps, and reduce research waste.
- If your research involves human participants, a DMP supports researchers in complying with the GDPR and avoid putting your participants at risk.

A typical DMP outlines:

- What data is being used: newly collected and/or existing data?
- What type and how much data will you produce.
- What is the [classification of the data](#) (based on confidentiality, availability, integrity)
- Where and how will you store your data.
- What documentation and metadata will accompany the data.
- Whether data will be deposited into a [data repository](#) and under which terms.
- What tools (hardware and software) you need to obtain and (re)use the data.
- What data protection and privacy measures will you take.
- What other legal matters you consider, such as intellectual property rights?
- How much budget is needed for the RDM costs (this is only a requirement for research projects with external funding).

TU/e expects researchers to use:

The [Research Cockpit](#) to write your DMP. The platform provides a template with the relevant questions that you will need to answer. On the TU/e [Data Management page](#), you can find the information you need to write your DMP. For any questions related to DMPs please contact your [dedicated research data steward](#).

For research projects that are part of a collaboration or contract research projects, a DMP is also required, however, if the collaborating party or contractor has a DMP for this project, there is no need to create a new one, this DMP only needs to be uploaded to the Research Cockpit.

For fully theoretical research projects we have created a highly simplified DMP for minimal research project data management and compliance purposes.

2. Ethical review/ Medical Ethical review

When you are working with human participants and/or processing personal data¹ it is mandatory to have ethical approval (Ethical Review Board / Medical Ethical Review). The purpose of an ethical review is to ensure that your research is in accordance with the ethical standards of research and is in accordance with existing laws and regulations. The Executive Board has mandated the ERB to review all research with human participants and/or personal data. Please note that when your project concerns medical scientific research and participants are subject to medical procedures, or it uses a medical device, the project is subject to the Law on [Medical Scientific Research involving Human Beings](#) (In Dutch Wet Medisch Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek, WMO).

Benefits of ethical approval:

- This ensures that your research follows the ethical research standards and is in accordance with existing laws and regulations.
- You will be ready to provide an ethical approval to a journal when publishing your findings.
- The ethical review ensures appropriate protection to the participants and the researchers, for instance on privacy matters.
- For medical research, you will ensure compliance with the law.

TU/e mandates:

The [Research Cockpit](#) platform to write your ethics application. More information is provided in the [Ethical Review page](#).

¹ Any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.

3. Storage solution during research

During your research, you need a place to store your research output. There are many ways to store and share your research data safely as your project progresses, along with other means to ensure data security. The best place to store your files depends on the number and size of your files, the required processing speed, type of data, data confidentiality, and whether only you need access, or you need to share data with external collaborators.

Furthermore, ensure the safety of your data by regularly backing it up to prevent loss and maintaining data security through the prevention of unauthorized access.

Benefits of using TU/e storage solutions:

- Saves you time in finding the data.
- Ensures data safety and prevents delays and frustration of data loss.
- Helps you comply with the GDPR.
- Saves time and effort having to move around files.
- Makes the sharing of files easier.

TU/e expects researchers to use:

TU/e's storage solutions for your research data. More information on storage tailored to your needs can be found in the [Storage Finder tool](#). Furthermore, tailored advice on data storing and sharing can be provided by the [Research IT consultants](#) of LIS Product area research and data stewards of the RDM support team (rdmsupport@tue.nl).

TU/e strongly discourage storing data on personal computers, external hard drives, or mobile phones due to irregular back-ups and high potential for loss of data. Storing data in cloud services outside the EU should also be avoided because of possible non-compliance with the GDPR.

4. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

When research at the TU/e contains personal data, it must comply with the personal data protection principles which are established in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the European data protection legislation. In the Netherlands, the GDPR is known as 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming' (AVG) and the Dutch legislator has created a national implementation law ([national implementation law \(the uAVG\)](#)).

In the GDPR [personal data](#) is defined as any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ("data subject"). The law distinguishes between regular category personal data and special categories of personal data. The latter is considered more sensitive by nature, and consequently the legislator has given additional obligations to institutes using these categories of personal data.

Processing of personal data refers to every action that is taken concerning personal data (e.g. collecting, recording, analysing, structuring, saving, modifying, using, aligning or combining, shielding, deleting or destroying data). This applies to both manual and automatic processes.

When working with personal data, the GDPR sets out a few obligations, including:

- Transparency. This entails providing information to the data subject on how their personal data is used for research purposes.
- Legitimate purpose. Personal data can only be used for this defined purpose and cannot be used for any other purposes.
- Data minimization. Only personal data required for/necessary to reach its research purpose(s) can be used in the research.
- Data protection. This includes measures like pseudonymization or anonymization of personal data as soon as possible and entering data agreements with research partners or data sharers.
- Legal basis for processing. The most common legal basis for processing personal data in research is the [public task](#) of the TU/e to conduct scientific research.

TU/e expect researchers to use:

For information on how to adhere to the GDPR in research and additional information on privacy, visit [this page](#). There is a [privacy e-learning course](#) for TU/e employees available to learn about the privacy basics. You can contact the [data steward of your department](#) to receive support on complying to the GDPR for their research projects.

5. Lawful Data Use - Data Agreements

In a research project, numerous parties may be involved, and when data is shared among them, arrangements for ownership, processing, and other aspects must be established through a data agreement. A data agreement is a contract in which you must write agreements regarding the processing and storage of the data concerned. This must be in writing but can also be digital.

Before (personal or IP-protected) data can be shared and/or a collaboration on research can take place, a data agreement needs to be approved by the Privacy Team and signed by the Managing Director of the corresponding department (or the Executive Board) and the other parties involved.

There are different forms of data agreements:

- Joint controllership agreement: when the research parties determine the means and purposes together (e.g. it is a collaboration between equal parties), they are both controllers.
- Data processing agreement: if one party determines the means and purposes (the controller) and another party processes data on behalf of the controller (the processor).
- Data sharing agreement: when one data controller transfers data to/shares data with another independent data controller and each work independently with that data. Such an agreement is also suitable for sharing anonymized data.

Benefits of data agreements:

- It establishes the responsibilities of the different parties involved.
- It indicates the legal obligations of each party, such as the requirements under the GDPR.
- It helps you clarify what can be done with the research data and under what conditions it can be shared.

TU/e expects researchers to use:

The TU/e has several templates available for different legal agreements. The TU/e data stewards can help you select the most suitable template and complete the first draft of it.

More information and templates of the legal agreements can be found in the [Privacy templates page](#).

6. FAIR Principles

The FAIR principles are a set of guiding principles that allow many different approaches to make data (including code) Findable, Accessible, and Interoperable, to serve the goal of Reusability. Making data and code FAIR does not necessarily mean “making them publicly available”. However, most funding bodies do require you to make your data FAIR and open when possible.

Making your data FAIR has several benefits:

- You increase the findability of your work and data, which leads to more citations.
- Your research can be reproduced easily, and it becomes more transparent, which further improves your research reliability.
- It helps other researchers (and your future self) understand the data and the research project.
- When your research is easily accessed, it enables more collaboration during your research and facilitates new collaborations in the future.
- When new collaborations emerge, it allows you to understand other perspectives and other research questions, increasing the impact of your data and work.

TU/e expects researchers to:

Make their data FAIR:

- ➔ Findable: It should be possible for others to discover your data and metadata. Data and metadata should be available online in a searchable [data repository](#), and should be assigned a persistent identifier.
- ➔ Accessible: It should be possible for both humans and machines to gain access to your data, under well-defined conditions.
- ➔ Interoperable: Data and metadata should conform to recognized formats and standards to allow them to be combined and exchanged between researchers and machines.
- ➔ Reusable: Documentation and metadata are needed to support data interpretation and reuse. The data, metadata, and documentation should be clearly licensed, so others know what kinds of reuse are permitted.

Note that software can also be made fair: [FAIR | FAIR \(fair-software.nl\)](#)

More information on how to make your data FAIR can be found on [FAIR Principles \(GO FAIR\)](#) and [Make your research data more FAIR \(How to FAIR\)](#).

7. Data package and data documentation

A data package contains the research data itself including all the information needed to understand and use the data. The information in the data package should be concise, yet as complete as possible for other researchers to reuse and/or recreate your study results independently and solely based on this information.

Benefits of creating a data package:

- Creating a data package allows you to tidy up after research.
- A data package serves as “evidence” to safeguard research integrity and ensure verifiability of research results.
- A data package can be a source of knowledge and inspiration for follow-up research and build upon for other researchers and your research team in the future.
- Many funders require you to deposit your data package into a [data repository](#).
- A data package allows you to only preserve the necessary data.

TU/e expects researchers to:

The data package should use file formats that are open, standardized, or commonly used. A data package should contain (some of the following files might not be applicable, depending on the type of research):

1. **README file:** this file should be in .txt format and the first document to consult when others access your data. It should provide a quick introduction to and an easy-to-understand description of your data so that the data can easily be navigated and searched.
2. **Metadata file:** metadata is “data about data”. It is standardized and structured information explaining the provenance of the data (i.e. when uploading your data or software to a repository, there is standardized data that must be filled-in, like, file name, author name, email, type of data, discipline, license, etc.).
3. **License file:** this file contains the legal terms and conditions under which the data can be used.
4. **Raw data files:** These are files containing the raw data as collected. However, be careful how you manage (raw) personal, medical, and other sensitive data in your data package. The research group or department can decide what raw data should be maintained and kept and what can be deleted.
5. **Processed data:** Using a processing script, raw data turns into processed data that is ready for analysis. These processed data files should also be added to the data package.
6. **Syntax files:** Scripts for processing data and analyzing data. Code scripts used to transform the raw data into processed data, code scripts used to analyze the data and produce the results, or any other code or syntax file important for others to reproduce your results. The code in the files should be accompanied by (inline) annotation/comments or other instructions on how to use the code.
7. **Protocols and Methodologies:** All protocols for the instruments used during the research, and a description of the methodology used in the project.

A good but sometimes daunting way to test the completeness of the data package is trying to establish whether you could recreate the results in the study yourself with only the information in the package.

Keywords: Policy, Research Data Management, Data Management Plan, Ethical Approval

Trefwoorden: Beleid, Onderzoek Data Management, Data Management Plan, Ethical Approval